

STRAINLESS MONOCYCLIC RINGS. PART II. SYNTHESIS OF 3-METHYLCYCLOHEXANE-1-CARBOXY-1-ACETIC ACID AND SEPARATION OF ITS ISOMERS

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The continuation of the work of the isolation of the isomeric *m*-methylcyclohexane-succinic acid has yielded four isomeric acids. These melt at different temperatures, the first one melting at 88°, the second melts at 99°, whilst the other two melt at 168° and 157° respectively. The mixed m. p. of the different pairs indicates by a distinct lowering of the m. p. that they are separate compounds. Such derivatives as anhydrides and anilic acids, as also their imides lead to the same conclusion. The solubility of the ammonium salts of the acids in absolute alcohol also points out that they are not identical in character. The acid (m.p. 88°) when converted into its anhydride, gives a liquid anhydride which on decomposition with water gives two acids one melting at 99° and the other at 157°, this is an example of the interconversion of the acids by which the less stable one passes into its more stable analogue.

In part I of this series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 277) the question of strain-free structure of *p*-methylcyclohexane ring has been discussed and definite evidence in favour of the same has been put forward. Uptil now no evidence could be obtained in support of a strain-free and consequently multiplanar configuration of cyclohexanone ring itself, due probably, to the unchecked intramolecular rotation of the carbon atoms forming the ring. The moment substituents enter into more than one carbon atom forming the ring, the free intramolecular rotational motion of the different members constituting the ring is more or less checked. Thus it is possible for 4-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (I) to exhibit the isomerism by virtue of the geometrical position of the different members taking part in the formation of the molecule.

(I)

(II)

Goldschmidt and Grafinger (*Ber.*, 1935, **68**, 279) have questioned the truth of the above statement, saying that they were unable to isolate the four different forms of the acid (I). It is rather surprising that the experiments that were repeated a number of times by one of us (M.Q.K.) with the same result, should be found altogether wrong. The work has again been repeated in this laboratory and the results obtained fully support our original view (*cf. Nature*, 1936, **138**, 301).

Our work with *m*- and *o*-methylcyclohexanones were nearing completion when Desai, Hunter, Gholam Khan and Saharia (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 416) published a paper on the same subject but they could not get more than two isomers with either the *meta*- or the *ortho*-compounds. But our findings were different; we got results which go in favour of our original findings and in fact four distinctly different acids have been isolated in case of *m*-methylcyclohexane derivative, the results of which are described here. We repeated the experiments a number of times and always obtained the same result. It may be incidentally mentioned that the work did not prove to be a very plain sailing one, on the other hand it has taken several years of very patient work for its completion. We find that the difference in the position of the substituent in the cyclohexane ring does not materially alter the behaviour of this ring from that of its *para*-isomer. In the boat shape configuration 3-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (II) will exist in two stereoisomeric modifications and in the chair shaped configuration again there will be possibility of the existence of two more stereoisomerides.

m-Methylcyclohexanone has been converted into the acid (II) through a series of reactions that are practically of the same nature as used in the previous case (Qudrat-i-Khuda, *loc. cit.*). Ethyl 3-methylcyclohexane-1-cyano-cyanoacetate (III) was obtained by the addition of potassium cyanide to ethyl 3-methylcyclohexylidene cyanoacetate (IV) in alcoholic solution. This ester was not isolated in pure condition, but was directly hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The dicyano ester (III) was found to be rather difficultly hydrolysable. Even after heating the acid mixture for nearly fifty hours, a small quantity of an acidic nitrogenous substance, a mixture of imides, could be isolated. As the product of hydrolysis a crude mixture was obtained, which consisted of several acids and the imide just referred to.

The separation of the acids was effected through the ammonium salt, which dissolved completely in hot absolute alcohol. A saturated alcoholic solution of the ammonium salts deposits on cooling part of it as a crystalline solid, which dissolves in water completely and on acidification gives a mixture of acids melting indefinitely between 78-85°. On repeated crystallisation from benzene, this can be separated into two portions one melting at 99° (B) and the other which is more soluble in benzene melting at 88° (A). The acid (B) gives an anhydride melting at 45°. The portion of the ammonium salt soluble in cold water gave a small quantity of a solid imide, insoluble in water and melting indefinitely between 138-144°. The aqueous solution being acidified gave a solid acid, mixed with an oily acidic substance. It is rather difficult to effect a complete separation of this solid from the viscous mass. The solid has, however, been separated by benzene in which it does not dissolve to any appreciable extent, and melts at 168° (C). It gives a liquid anhydride. The benzene mother-liquor on being treated with petroleum ether gives some more of the solid acid, m. p. 168°. The benzene-petrol mother-liquor, on evaporation of the solvent, gave a thick oily liquid which on esterification followed by hydrolysis gave a new acid (D) (along with some others) which is freely soluble in benzene and melts at 157°.

The ammonium salts of the pure acids A, B, C and D were found to have the following solubilities in alcohol:

Acids.	The amount of boiling alcohol required to dissolve 2 g. of the ammonium salt.	The amount of the ammonium salt that crystallised out at ordinary temp. (28-30°)
A (m.p. 88°)	46 c.c.	0.2 g.
B (m.p. 99°)	72	0.7
C (m.p. 168°)	25	Nil.
D (m.p. 157°)	44	Only traces.

During the repetitions of these experiments, it has always been observed that the quantities of the isolable acids varied in different experiments, and it has not yet been possible to find an optimum condition for the best yield

of any of these acids. It has, however, been generally found that the quantity of the acids (A and B) depends somewhat on the duration of heating in the hydrolysis of the condensation product (III). When it was hydrolysed for about 30 hours, the quantity of this acid mixture was found to be only 15 g., whereas by increasing the period of heating to 46-50 hours, the yield increased to 70 g. for each 100 g. of the unsaturated ester (IV) employed in condensation with potassium cyanide in either of the experiments, other conditions remaining identical.

The isolation of the four isomeric acids in this case, and a comparison of these with the acids derived from *p*-methylcyclohexanone (m. p. 137°, 129°, 174° and 146°) decides conclusively that none of the isomers of the acid (I) is structurally identical with those now obtained.

The liquid anhydride of the acid A (m. p. 88°), when heated with water gave a mixture of acids from which an acid, m. p. 99° and another, m. p. 157°, have been isolated, but the change does not take place by heating (A) alone with water or with hydrochloric acid. It is perhaps this tendency of the less stable acid to pass over to its more stable analogue, that causes the difference in the total yield of the acids, as referred to above.

It also occurred to us that some of these acids might be eutectic mixtures of the others, but a comparative examination of the mixed m. p. of the acids and those of their derivatives, left no room for doubts regarding the individuality of all the four acids. The acid (A) is much more soluble in cold benzene than the acid (B) and the acid (D) is extremely soluble in the same solvent in the cold, while (C) does not dissolve in it even when boiled. The anilic acid of (D) is soluble in cold benzene, whereas the other anilic acids are practically insoluble in the same solvent. The imide of acid (A) melts at 138°, while that of the acid (B) melts at 91°, which suggests that the acid (A) may not be an impure mixture of acid (B). Many attempts were made to crystallise mixtures of different acids, two at a time, but never could an eutectic mixture be obtained from these experiments.

TABLE I.

M. p. of the acids.			Mixed m. p. of the acids.		
A	...	88°	A & B	...	92-93°
B	...	99°	A & D	...	89-91°
C	...	168°	A & C	...	125-130°
	...	157°	B & D	...	101°
			B & C	...	118-122°
			C & D	...	160°

TABLE II.

M. p. of the pure anilic acids.			Mixed m. p. of the anilic acids.		
W from A	...	166°	W & X	...	160°
X from B	...	180°	W & Y	...	145°
Y from D	...	171°	W & Z	...	158°
Z from C	...	173°	X & Y	...	150°
			X & Z	...	156-57°
			Y & Z	...	158°

TABLE III.

M. p. of the imides.			Mixed m. p. of the imides.		
M from A	...	138°	M & N	...	89-90°
N from B	...	91°	M & O	...	167-171°
O from C	...	183°	M & P	...	153-155°
P from D	...	176°	N & O	...	138-140°
			N & P	...	120-123°
			O & P	...	180°

The work on the isolation of the corresponding acids of the *ortho*-series, is also complete and these will be described in a subsequent paper. The results obtained suggest that none of those acids is identical with any of the acids hitherto described in the *para*- and *meta*-series. Thus the possibility of the admixtures of different methylcyclohexanones in the samples of the ketones used as starting materials, have been precluded.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl 3-methylcyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate was obtained by the condensation of *m*-methylcyclohexanone and ethyl cyanoacetate in equimolecular proportion in 76% yield, b. p. 192°/60 mm. or 178-179°/28 mm; d_4^{20} , 1.01829; n_D^{20} , 1.48544 $(R_L)_D = 58.31$, (Calc.: C, 56.36, Exaltation is due to the conjugated system, cf. Perkin, Hardinge and Haworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1958).

3-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid was prepared by the condensation of ethyl 3-methylcyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate (100 g.) with potassium cyanide (60 g.) dissolved in rectified spirit (430 c. c.). The

alcohol was removed under reduced pressure from a water-bath. The residue, which consisted of the potassium compound of the condensation product with some unchanged potassium cyanide was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (700 c. c.) and then heated on a sand bath for 36 hours. The acid solution when cooled, gave on extraction with ether a thick viscous mass. This was freed from any neutral product by dissolving in a solution of sodium carbonate, which yielded a mixture of acids weighing 100 g. The mixture of acids was separated as follows:

The mixture of acids was digested with ammonia till a distinct smell of ammonia was observed. The product was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the residual viscous mass was treated with just enough hot absolute alcohol (400 c. c.). The solution on being cooled deposited crystals of ammonium salt which were filtered off and the solvent removed by distillation. The aqueous solution of the solid ammonium salt yielded on acidification an oily substance. The oily acid was extracted with ether and after removal of the solvent the residue gradually solidified in a vacuum desiccator. The solid thus obtained was crystallised from benzene, when the m. p. began to rise gradually. After nine crystallisations no further rise in the m. p. was noticed. The acid, however, crystallises out along with some benzene and true m. p. cannot be obtained until it has been left to dry for some time. The combination is a loose one and on leaving it for some time at the ordinary temperature, the benzene goes away completely. The sample for analysis was obtained after twelve crystallisations when it came out in small cubes melting sharply at 99° . (Found: C, 59.9; H, 8.3; M. W. by titration, 200. $C_{10}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0 per cent. M. W., 200).

The *anhydride* of this acid was obtained by heating it with acetic anhydride, b. p. $152-53^{\circ}/10$ mm. It solidified into beautiful rhombic cubes, m. p. 45° , in a vacuum desiccator. When aniline and this anhydride were mixed together in equimolecular proportion and shaken well the *anilic acid* crystallised out readily. This was purified through its sodium salt and re-crystallised from rectified spirit in hexagonal laminae, m. p. 170° . (Found: C, 70.0; H, 8.0. $C_{16}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 69.8; H, 7.6 per cent). The *anil*, obtained from this anilic acid, crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 115° (Found: C, 74.7; H, 7.4. $C_{16}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 74.7; H, 7.4 per cent).

p-Toluidinamic acid, obtained from the anhydride and *p*-toluidine, crystallises from rectified spirit, m. p. 172° . (Found: C, 70.3; H, 7.9. $C_{17}H_{23}O_2N$ requires C, 70.6; H, 7.9 per cent). When *p*-toluidinamic acid was heated at 190° it decomposed and gave the corresponding *imide* which after being washed with a solution of sodium carbonate, crystallised from

alcohol, in small rhombic plates, m. p. 98° . (Found: C, 75.3; H, 7.9. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 75.3; H, 7.8 per cent).

β -Naphthylamic acid, obtained from the same anhydride in the usual way, crystallised from rectified spirit, m. p. 182° . (Found: C, 73.7; H, 7.2. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 73.8; H, 7.0 per cent). *β -Naphthylimide* crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 118° . (Found: C, 78.9; H, 6.5. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 78.4; H, 6.8 per cent).

The *imide* of the acid was obtained by heating the ammonium salt at the ordinary pressure when it decomposed and gave a solid product which was insoluble in water. This was then washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit, m. p. 91° . (Found: C, 66.1; H, 8.3. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 66.3; H, 8.3 per cent).

From the benzene mother-liquor of the acid (B), the solvent was removed and the residue was crystallised again from benzene. The mother-liquor contained a low melting acid which was obtained as a crystalline solid, m. p. 88° (Found: C, 59.9; H, 7.9 per cent. M. W. 203). This acid (A) is much more soluble in benzene than the acid (B). It does not ordinarily come out from excess of this solvent. It can easily be converted into the anhydride which was obtained as a liquid at the ordinary temperature, b. p. $207^{\circ}/35$ mm, and gave an *anilic acid* which separated out from the benzene solution of the anhydride and aniline. It crystallises from rectified spirit in rhombic plates, m. p. 166° (Found: C, 69.9; H, 7.8 per cent). The corresponding *anil* was prepared by decomposing the anilic acid at 180° and it crystallised from alcohol in prismatic needles and melted at 100° (Found: C, 74.8; H, 7.4 per cent). *p-Toluidinamic acid* separated in large plates from alcohol, m. p. at 172° (Found: C, 71.02; H, 7.9 per cent). The *p-toluidinimide* crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. at 78° (Found: C, 75.7; H, 7.9 per cent). The *imide* was prepared by the decomposition of the ammonium salt. It was found to be rather soluble in rectified spirit, but crystallised out from dilute alcohol in small cubes, m. p. $138-39^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 8.4 per cent).

The portion of the ammonium salt that remained in alcoholic solution was obtained as a viscous mass on the removal of the solvent. This was then treated with cold water, when most of it dissolved leaving a small quantity which on crystallisation from dilute spirit melted indefinitely between $138-144^{\circ}$. The aqueous solution on acidification gave a mixture of the acids which on being treated with hot benzene left a crystalline insoluble solid, while the oily portion dissolved in it completely. The benzene mother-liquor on being cooled and treated with petroleum (b. p. $70-80^{\circ}$) gave some more of the same solid acid. This acid could be crystallised from ethyl

acetate in large hexagonal prisms, m.p. 168° [Found: C, 59.8; H, 8.1 per cent. M. W. by (titration) 200]. When this acid (C) (5.9 g.) was treated with acetic anhydride (7 c.c.) and the product distilled, the resulting *anhydride* boiled at $159^{\circ}/9$ mm. and gave an *anilic acid* crystallising from dilute alcohol in rhombic plates, m.p. 173° (Found: C, 69.8; H, 7.7 per cent). The *anilic acid* decomposed at $180-190^{\circ}$ and yielded the *anil* which crystallised from spirit in long prisms, m.p. 136° (Found: C, 74.6; H, 7.3 per cent). *p-Toluidin amic acid* crystallised from spirit in rhombic plates, m.p. 182° (Found: C, 70.5; H, 8.3 per cent). The corresponding *p-toluidinimide* came out from alcohol in well defined long prisms, m.p. 141° (Found: C, 75.7; H, 7.9 per cent). β -*Naphthylamid acid* was prepared in the usual way and crystallises from dilute alcohol, m.p. 191° (Found: C, 78.6; H, 6.4 per cent). The *imide* corresponding to this naphthylamic acid crystallises in small cubes from alcohol, m.p. 189° (Found: C, 77.9; H, 6.6 per cent). The *imide* obtained from the ammonium salt of this acid (C) crystallised from spirit in small cubes, m.p. 183° (Found: C, 66.7; H, 8.3 per cent).

The benzene-petroleum mother-liquor from the acid (D) was heated on the water-bath to distil off the solvents. The residue did not solidify even on being left for several months in a vacuum desiccator. It was then esterified by heating on the water-bath with five times its weight of absolute alcohol and 5 % sulphuric acid. The nature of the product of esterification depended upon the duration of heating. When the mixture was heated for 5 hours, the product consisted of an acid portion, which was converted into the calcium salt and found on analysis to be the calcium salt of the acid ester of the succinic acid (II). Hydrolysis of this acid ester with hydrochloric acid (15%), gave acid (B) as the only product. The neutral portion consisted of an ester, b.p. $153^{\circ}/17$ mm; d_4^{20} , 1.03682 n_D^{20} , 1.45677 whence $[R_L]_D$ found, 67.3, calc., 67.9. This ester on being hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid gave a mixture of acids from which benzene precipitated a crystalline solid, which recrystallised from ethyl acetate and melted at 168° and was found to be identical with acid (C). The benzene mother-liquor on evaporation of the solvent deposited a crystalline solid, which could be crystallised from a small quantity of the solvent in small plates, m.p. 157° . (Found: C, 59.7; H, 7.8 per cent. M., W., 203). When boiled with acetic anhydride it gave an *anhydride* which distilled at $232^{\circ}/55$ mm. and solidified on being left in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 66° . When the anhydride was mixed in benzene solution with aniline at first no precipitate was obtained. On keeping for some time and shaking, a very small quantity of a crystalline solid separated out. The benzene mother-liquor was, therefore, heated on the water-bath till the solvent was completely removed and a

crystalline residue was obtained. The *anilic acid* thus prepared was purified in the usual way when it came out in large plates from dilute alcohol, m.p. 171°. (Found: C, 70.4; H, 7.9 per cent). The *imide* of the acid was prepared as in the previous cases. It crystallised from rectified spirit in small cubes, m.p. 176-77°. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 8.5 per cent).

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